

A New Coating for Reducing Wind Turbine Blade Lightning Damage

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Keywords: lightning protection system, wind energy, wind turbine, wind turbine blade, flashover, topcoat

1. ABSTRACT

A novel wind turbine blade coating has been developed that reduces lightning damage to the blades. It enhances the effectiveness of existing lightning protection systems comprised of a down conductor and one or more surface mounted lightning receptors. It can be applied as a retrofit to existing turbines or applied to new blades. The coating contains small discrete conductive elements that locally enhance the electric field in the air above the elements to promote the early formation of a surface flashover. This helps leaders emanating from the existing receptors travel faster and farther over the blade surface to connect with the downward stepped leader from the clouds before competing streamers that originate from the blade's interior have a chance to puncture through the skin and cause damage. A key feature of the coating is that it does not provide a conductive pathway for the strike. Rather, it enables a conductive channel of ionized air adjacent to and above the surface. This non-sacrificial operation allows the coating to remain effective and undamaged even after multiple strikes.

The coating was empirically developed over the past three years using extensive small-scale and large-scale high voltage and high current testing. The first phase consisted of testing flashovers across small samples up to 100 mm in length with voltages up to 70 kV. Subsequent optimization used 610 mm square panels combined with a 2-meter air gap in a high voltage lab capable of reaching 2.4 MV. The material, size, shape, and concentration of the elements in the coating were carefully optimized to a narrow range of parameters found to be most effective. For the final formulation, the metric of average flashover time was reduced, on average, by 76% compared to a baseline topcoat. The coating's mechanical performance was also tested to ensure the improved lightning protection does not come at the expense of the other functions a topcoat is designed to perform. Photos demonstrate the desired increase in streamer and leader activity around the lightning receptor with the coating. Excellent damage resistance was verified with full-scale currents up to 200 kA. Finally, the coating was validated with IEC standard initial leader attachment tests on GE 1.5sle wind turbine blade tips 5 meters in length. Results showed a significant increase in the level of protection with the coating properly applied compared to a blade without the coating. If applied to operational turbines, a 73% reduction in punctures was estimated. Field

tests are scheduled on multiple turbines at two operational wind farms beginning in the summer of 2022.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Motivation

Every year, the global wind industry loses \$100M or more to damage caused by lightning. Already susceptible to lightning because of their height, wind turbines have an even higher probability of being struck than a stationary metal tower of comparable size due to the rotation of the blades and the materials used in their construction [1]. The issue is further exacerbated by the fact that a lightning strike is typically considered a force majeure event, not covered by manufacturer warranties, and not always covered by insurance. The damage that lightning inflicts on the wind industry is expected to get worse in the future as the number of wind farms grows, the average turbine height increases, and the effects of climate change intensify [2].

2.2 Background

Most modern wind turbine blades are equipped with lightning protection systems (LPS). The most common LPS uses one or more surface-mounted lightning receptors connected to a grounded down conductor (see Fig. 1) [4,5]. A typical lightning strike begins when the strong electric field induced by a charged storm cloud and downward stepped leader causes upward streamers and leaders to emanate from the grounded lightning receptors on the blade. A direct strike results when one of the upward leaders from the receptor connects with the downward stepped leader from the cloud passing a large amount of electrical charge [5].

Fig. 1. Diagram of a typical wind turbine blade lightning strike and LPS.

Unfortunately, this system has some flaws. Streamers on the blade can frequently originate from the internal down conductor (or other metallic components inside the blade) instead of the receptors, leading to, at best, small punctures in the skin and, at worst, split trailing edges or major delaminations [5]. Punctures, if left untreated, also allow moisture to infiltrate the blade, which can weaken the structure over time and may lead to catastrophic damage from subsequent strikes creating explosive increases in steam pressure.

Even when upward leaders originating from inside the blade do not connect to form a direct strike, they can penetrate the skin and weaken the structure. Over time, this can reduce the blade skin's insulating properties, making it more susceptible to future lightning damage.

2.3 Current Approaches to Lightning Protection

The wind industry has made improvements to the standard LPS designs over the years. These advances have come from direct field experience, design iteration, and significant research and development. Simple improvements to the down conductor such as using a well-insulated cable with a circular cross section placed in the center of the blade have helped to reduce the likelihood of streamers emanating from them compared to legacy designs using bolted rectangular bars or flat braids (which contain sharp edges that magnify the electric field strength) placed near the skin. Adding additional pairs of surface receptors farther inboard and conductive metal tips are also beneficial. With the increasing use of carbon fiber in blade construction, additional elements like expanded metal foils and meshes are also becoming common.

Despite these improvements, there are still several problems responsible for the industry's continued high operations and maintenance expenses related to lightning damage. First, legacy blade models, such as those installed before 2012, generally have more simplistic LPS designs. Combined with the age and general wear on these machines, they are often prone to significant annual lightning damage and associated repair costs and downtime. Second, given the fast pace of turbine model development and release, some modern blades have design flaws responsible for consistent lightning damage seen in the field. Finally, even modern designs with good protection schemes will gradually become more susceptible to lightning damage over the turbine's twenty to thirty-year lifetime. Leading edge erosion and other physical damage can create weak spots in the blade. Continued operation in high electric fields also reduces the insulating ability of the blade skin. Past lightning damage, even when repaired appropriately, can still increase the likelihood of subsequent damage. All these issues suggest the use of retrofit solutions that can be easily applied to provide improved lightning protection.

The most common retrofit device is the segmented (or lightning) diverter strip. This device originated in the aviation industry for use on radomes to protect the sensitive equipment contained within from lightning damage while allowing the radome to remain transparent to radar at critical transmission frequencies [6]. Segmented diverters consist of a linear array of discrete conductive elements precisely placed on a dielectric strip with small gaps between adjacent elements. On a typical wind turbine, three diverter strips are placed from the

receptor leading towards the leading edge, trailing edge, and blade tip on both the suction and pressure sides of the blade.

In the strong electric field prior to a strike, the air between adjacent conductors in a segmented diverter ionizes. As the electric field intensifies, these discrete points of ionization merge creating a highly conductive pathway to the receptor through the air above the surface. When the full stroke current occurs, the electrical and thermal energy is largely transferred above the blade's surface to the receptors in a flashover. When operating as intended, this ionization channel will form early and connect with a downward stepped leader before other streamers inside the blade have a chance to cause damage. While well-established in the aviation industry, these devices have limitations for use in the wind industry.

2.4 A Novel Lightning Protection Coating

Arctura has developed a new coating-based solution intended to enhance the performance of existing lightning protection systems on wind turbine blades. The technology consists of a proprietary formulation of minute conductive elements of a specific size, shape, and material combined with an industry-standard topcoat at a specific concentration. Topcoat refers to the outer, final paint layers applied to the blade that protect it against environmental effects, including rain erosion, UV degradation, and particle impacts, as well as providing the preferred color and finish. The proprietary additive consists of common, non-toxic components, and does not require exotic manufacturing processes, thereby minimizing cost. The new coating is named ArcGuide™.

The ArcGuide™ coating itself is not a current-carrying conductor. Instead, prior to a lightning strike, the minute conductive particles in the coating perturb the electric field on the surface of the blade resulting in spots of early ionization in the air adjacent to the surface. As the electric field continues to increase, these spots of ionized air facilitate the formation of streamers and then leaders along the surface earlier than they would otherwise occur without the coating. When applied on a blade around a lightning receptor, the coating enables more leaders to emanate from the receptor and enables them to travel farther and faster. This makes it more probable that a downward stepped lightning leader will connect to the receptor as opposed to puncturing through the blade skin elsewhere causing damage. During the return stroke, the massive amount of electrical and thermal energy is passed in a highly conductive channel of ionized gas above the surface in a surface flashover, leaving the coating largely unaffected.

2.5 Design Considerations

The primary focus during the development of the ArcGuide™ coating was its electrical performance and survivability, but cost, color, mechanical properties, weatherability, and surface roughness were also important considerations.

Key to the coating's success is its electrical performance. The goal was to encourage early streamer and leader formation from existing lightning receptors. This was accomplished by creating surface flashovers along candidate coatings first on small-scale benchtop samples, then larger square panels, and eventually MW-scale wind turbine blade tips. Photos were used to assess the characteristics of the flashover. The voltage and time to flashover were used to quantify performance and optimize parameters. In addition to flashover testing, panels and blade tips were photographed at high DC voltages to

qualitatively assess how the coating affects streamer and leader formation in the high electric fields that exist just before a flashover.

Another critical design goal is the survivability of the coating. The coating is not intended to be sacrificial, as it would be impractical to reapply it regularly. Any evidence in photos of conduction through the coating as opposed to flashing over the surface is undesirable. To evaluate this consideration, full-threat lightning stroke currents up to 200 kA were used to assess degradation.

Achieving an affordable coating is important given the cost constraints of wind farm owner-operators. To support this, exotic materials or manufacturing methods were avoided.

The color of the coating was noted to drastically darken or change with some preliminary additives. While not a primary concern, matching the white or gray colors (RAL 9010 and 7035 respectively) typically found on wind turbine blades was preferable. On some farms, specific colors are contractually required.

The coating also needs to maintain the same mechanical properties of traditional industry topcoat. Topcoats are expected to provide many years of maintenance-free operation to protect the blade without eroding or otherwise failing. The primary metrics tested were pull-off strength and adhesion per ASTM standards.

Weatherability, particularly corrosion resistance, was assessed using an accelerated salt fog test as well as a non-accelerated test with samples kept outside for many months.

Smoother coatings are generally preferred, however, additives tested were usually large enough to increase the surface roughness of the coating. Roughness was quantified at a third-party lab using a profilometer as well as qualitatively assessed. The biggest practical concern is the potential for increased fouling, though the extent and implication of this is not well understood.

3. COATING DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Small-scale Testing

Initial coating development was conducted in Arctura's lab using a high voltage DC power supply (Glassman EJ06R100). Candidate coatings were applied to 50x100 mm fiberglass substrates placed between high voltage and ground electrodes. The power supply voltage was linearly increased over many seconds to produce a surface flashover adjacent to the coating. Typical flashovers were 50 mm in length and up to 70 kV. Voltage and current traces were recorded as well as photographs of the flashover to both quantitatively and qualitatively assess performance.

This small-scale empirical testing allowed a range of coating additive parameters to be efficiently evaluated. The considered parameters were material, size, shape, and concentration in the topcoat. The quantitative figure of merit was the voltage at which a flashover occurred. The objective was to find a formula that minimized this flashover voltage.

Hundreds of tests were conducted throughout this test period. Many showed no reduction in flashover voltage compared to baseline. Many others showed a sizable reduction in voltage, but photos revealed the discharge passed through the coating

and not in the air above the surface. While this conduction through the coating did not result in damage at small-scale, damage would be expected at full-scale lightning currents, which is undesirable. A relatively narrow range of parameters, however, did result in exterior flashovers at reduced voltages. Fig. 2 shows a long-exposure photo of a surface flashover along one of the formulations which depicts the theory of operation well. Conductive elements in the topcoat promote spots of early ionization in the air adjacent to them. In the increasing electric field, these spots eventually merge, creating a highly conductive channel of ionized gas above the surface.

Fig. 2. Long exposure photo of a successful small-scale coating test showing early spots of ionization and the surface flashover that follows.

3.2 Panel Testing

After small-scale testing, ten candidate formulations were applied to 610 mm square fiberglass panels representative of wind turbine blade skin. A washer was bolted to the center of the panels to represent a lightning receptor. These panels were tested in the high voltage lab at Lightning Technologies, an NTS Company. The center receptor was connected to the output of a 2.4 MV Marx generator, and the panel was suspended 2 m above and perpendicular to the ground plane on the floor. This is the reverse of the real-world scenario where the receptor is grounded and the clouds overhead are charged, however, the governing physics are the same, and this is a well-validated standard practice [4]. Fig. 3 shows a photo of the setup and typical strike.

The applied voltages are representative of real-world conditions, and the results are valid for determining the path that the full stroke current would take during an actual lightning strike. The initial tests were qualitative, and candidates were favored when the discharge flashed over along the surface as opposed to connecting directly to the receptor through the air or conducting through the coating. Only a subset of candidates showed consistent surface flashovers for both positive and negative polarities with no evidence of conduction through the coating.

Fig. 3. Typical high voltage panel test setup and surface flashover.

The same samples were then tested in Lightning Technologies' high current lab. Here, panels were subjected to full-threat lightning currents up to 200 kA but at lower voltages that necessitated initiating the path with a thin wire which was quickly vaporized. These tests were performed to evaluate any degradation of the coating that may result from a lightning stroke current. A typical stroke current arc is seen in Fig. 4. After multiple discharges, the surfaces of the panels were visually evaluated for damage. Most showed no signs of damage (Fig. 5, top), but in some cases there were tracking marks (Fig. 5, bottom) indicating some degradation of the coating had occurred. In this example, the coating seen in the bottom image contained a higher concentration of conductive elements compared to the coating in the top image. The more diffuse discoloration seen on both panels are deposits from the vaporized initiating wire and vaporized electrode metal and are not indicative of damage. After this testing, the best performing coating formula from both the high voltage and high current tests was selected for further optimization.

Fig. 4. High current discharge along the surface of a test panel.

Fig. 5. Detail of panels with lightning receptor at right after 200 kA high current tests showing no degradation (top) and tracking marks and some degradation (bottom).

It should be noted that in laboratory testing the stroke current necessarily comes immediately after the high voltage has established an ionized path, which allows no time for the electric arc ("channel") to lift off the blade surface. In natural lightning strikes, the electric field establishes the leader several milliseconds before a stroke current can appear, in which event the arc is no longer in contact with the coated surface. That is why tracking marks are rarely observed on surfaces of blades that have experienced stroke currents.

High voltage testing of panels proved to be the most useful means of further coating development. For these tests, a

standard switching impulse voltage waveform was used with the polarity and peak amplitude held constant (typically -275 kV). This waveform is most likely to represent the electric field from an approaching lightning leader, as compared with the much shorter duration voltage from the lightning impulse voltage waveform. The primary metric used to evaluate the coatings was the "flashover time" (i.e., the time from the start of the switching impulse voltage waveform application to when a flashover occurs). If a flashover occurs during the linearly increasing phase of the waveform, time and voltage are roughly proportional, but sometimes a flashover will occur after the peak when the voltage is decreasing, creating ambiguity if flashover voltage alone is used as a metric.

A lower flashover time is desirable. The goal of the coating is to promote earlier leader formation around the receptor so it can connect with a downward leader from the cloud before a leader emanating from an internal conductor can. In this way, the blade skin is saved from the damage that would occur had the massive charge of a lightning strike transferred through it.

Lightning is inherently stochastic and day-to-day atmospheric variations can also affect results. To account for this, each formulation was tested at least 12 times (3 strikes on each of the four sides of the square panel) to gain sufficient confidence in the mean flashover time, and a baseline panel was retested with each new study. Sensitivity to different additive parameters were tested and values were optimized. Fig. 6 is one example of many studies used to optimize parameters. In this case, different additive materials (currently, these are proprietary) were compared. The chart shows typical flashover times and relative uncertainties for these tests. Material 2 was ultimately chosen. While material 3 outperformed based on this metric alone, in high current testing, it showed minor signs of tracking damage and was discounted as a candidate.

In addition to the additives themselves, different topcoat types and thicknesses were tested. From these, a final optimized formulation was selected. Across multiple studies comparing the final optimized formulation to a baseline industry-standard topcoat, the mean percent reduction in flashover time ranged from 67-84% with an average of 76%.

Fig. 6. A comparison of flashover times for coating formulations with different additive materials compared to a baseline topcoat with no additives. Lower flashover times are preferred.

3.3 Mechanical Testing

While electrical performance was the primary development focus, the mechanical properties of the coating were also evaluated. It is important that modifications to improve lightning protection do not come at the expense of the topcoat's primary purpose: acting as an environmental barrier to protect the blade from weather; providing wear resistance; and acting as an attractive finish. A baseline topcoat and ArcGuide™ coating were both mechanically tested using industry-standard ASTM tests for coatings. ASTM D454, D6677, and D359 methods were used to evaluate pull-off strength, adhesion by knife, and adhesion by tape respectively. Tests were done both in-house and at a third-party certified test facility. Results to date do not indicate any reduction in mechanical strength or adhesion. Following ASTM D1654, a salt fog test was also conducted to evaluate corrosion resistance with different additive materials. While many formulations did show evidence of corrosion, the final ArcGuide™ coating formulation performed well.

Surface roughness profiles of the coating were also taken and analyzed. Compared to a baseline topcoat, the ArcGuide™ coating is rougher. The arithmetic average roughness, Ra, was measured to be 6.4 μm for the ArcGuide™ coating compared with 2.2 μm for the baseline topcoat. This is most apparent when viewed under a microscope as seen in Fig. 7. While efforts were taken to minimize roughness, smoother candidate coating formulations did not perform as well in flashover testing. However, simulations showed that the aerodynamic effect of roughness at this scale is negligible. Both the baseline and ArcGuide™ measurement are well below the industry-standard specification for wind turbine blade coatings (Ra < 30 μm).

Fig. 7. Microscope images of baseline topcoat (left) and ArcGuide™ coating (right) showing increased surface roughness.

4. COATING VALIDATION

4.1 Panel Streamer Visualization

The ArcGuide™ coating works by encouraging earlier and enhanced streamer and leader activity around the receptors than would otherwise occur without the coating. This activity was assessed visually in the high voltage lab using both square fiberglass panels and wind turbine blade tips. The panels and blade tips were subjected to a high DC voltage simulating the electric field moments before a lightning strike, and a photo of the streamer and leader activity was captured.

One such test used a panel coated with the ArcGuide™ coating on the left half and a baseline topcoat on the right half. The panel was arranged such that both halves were subject to the same initial electric field conditions. A mock lightning receptor was installed at the center of the panel. Fig. 8 shows the resulting photo. The outline of the panel, center receptor, and dividing line between the coatings have been highlighted.

Increased streamer and leader activity is clearly seen on the left side (coated with ArcGuide™ coating) relative to the right side (coated with baseline topcoat). This was observed in all trials. As previously discussed, this increased activity is key to guiding strikes to the receptor and thus reducing the probability of punctures and damage elsewhere on the blade.

Fig. 8. Panel streamer and leader visualization comparing the ArcGuide™ coating (left half) and baseline topcoat (right half).

4.2 Blade Tip Streamer Visualization

Several wind turbine blade tips from GE 1.5sle wind turbines were obtained after being retired from field use. This turbine model was chosen because it is the most common machine operating in the United States today [3] and is known to suffer from lightning damage. Different blade variations exist depending on the time of production and manufacturer. The results presented here are all for a “37C” variety which has a single large lightning receptor only on the pressure side of the blade near the tip. Typical blade tips tested were 5 meters in length and had some existing damage from years of operation.

An initial hypothesis was that the ArcGuide™ coating would offer maximum protection when applied over the entire blade tip. Streamer photos, however, showed this to be incorrect. Streamer and leader formation on a blade tip coated entirely with the ArcGuide™ coating (top) is compared to a baseline blade (bottom) in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Photos of GE 1.5sle blades at 10° showing increased leader formation on the ArcGuide™ coated blade (top) compared to a blade with a standard topcoat (bottom).

Compared to baseline, the ArcGuide™-coated blade increased streamer and leader activity around the tip receptor as desired. However, strong leaders also formed farther inboard, presumably emanating from parts of the down conductor with an elevated electric field (e.g., at a bolt) and through “weak points” in the blade skin. The presence of these undesired leaders will deteriorate the blade skin over time whenever high electric fields are present. They also compete with the leaders from the receptor to connect to a downward stepped leader from the cloud. If they do connect, it could result in severe damage. These photos indicate that the ArcGuide™ coating is likely most effective when only applied in the vicinity of the receptors. This was the application configuration used in subsequent tests.

4.3 High Voltage Blade Tip Test Setup

The effectiveness of the ArcGuide™ coating at reducing punctures was assessed using high voltage initial leader attachment tests per Annex D of IEC 61400-24 [4]. The IEC standard summarizes lightning risk, testing, and general protection requirements for the wind industry. The standard calls for the blade tip to be suspended over a ground plane with the receptor at high voltage as depicted in Fig. 10. The blade was tested at angles of 60°, 30°, and 10° with respect to the ground plane. Shallower angles are harder to protect as the electric field is increased inboard and away from the tip receptor.

At each angle, the blade was rotated to different orientations to allow each side of the blade to experience the highest electric field. Fig. 11 shows a diagram of the angles and orientations.

Fig. 10. Example of initial leader attachment test setup A (taken from IEC 61400-24 [4]).

Three trials (“strikes”) were conducted for each orientation. The blade was at negative polarity for all tests and the waveform and peak voltage were kept constant. Photos of each strike were captured, and the strike behavior (i.e., puncture or flashover to the receptor) was categorized based on the path seen in the photo. Suspected punctures were further confirmed by inspecting the blade for damage. For a given angle (60°, 30°, and 10°), if any strike at any orientation resulted in a puncture, that angle was denoted as “FAIL”. If all three strikes for all orientations for an angle successfully flashed over to the receptor, that angle was denoted as “PASS”. After each puncture, the resulting hole was patched with 5-minute epoxy. This helped increase the insulation resistance at that damage point, but the location remained a weak spot in subsequent tests.

Fig. 11. Possible angles and orientation for the initial leader attachment test setup A (taken from IEC 61400-24 [4]).

Statistically significant quantitative results pose a challenge for this type of testing. The stochastic nature of lightning means many tests are required to gain confidence. Every test, however, also electrically weakens the blade, and using a “new” blade for every test is not feasible. Furthermore, the blade tips tested in the lab were far from new due to lightning strikes and other wear and tear over years of use in the field. To minimize these biases as best as possible, tests were conducted on three different blades of similar age and condition. Tests for each blade configuration were ordered from least to most likely to puncture to minimize degradation and repair work. Each blade was also tested in both baseline and ArcGuide™ configurations. For blades #1 and #3, the baseline configuration was tested first and then the ArcGuide™ coating was applied. For blade #2, the ArcGuide™ coating was applied first, then it was sanded off and a baseline topcoat was applied before testing again.

4.4 High Voltage Blade Tip Test Results and Analysis

Table 1 shows the results of the high voltage initial leader attachment tests. The arrows denote the order in which the configurations (Baseline or ArcGuide™) for each blade were tested. Fig. 12 shows composite images all the strikes for the 60° angle for Blade #3. For the baseline configuration, two punctures inboard of the receptor can be seen, indicating a “FAIL” result for this angle. For the ArcGuide™ configuration, all strikes flashed over the exterior surface to the receptor indicating a “PASS” result.

Table 1. GE 1.5sle blade tip initial leader attachment test results.

Blade #1		
	Baseline →	ArcGuide™
60°	PASS	PASS
30°	PASS	PASS
10°	FAIL	FAIL
Blade #2		
	Baseline ←	ArcGuide™
60°	PASS	PASS
30°	FAIL	PASS
10°	FAIL	PASS
Blade #3		
	Baseline →	ArcGuide™
60°	FAIL	PASS
30°	FAIL	PASS
10°	FAIL	FAIL

Fig. 12. Composite images of all strikes to blade #3 at 60°. The baseline configuration (left) shows the fail condition (punctures) while the ArcGuide™ configuration (right) shows the pass condition (all flashovers to the receptor).

These results are encouraging. The only angle that experienced punctures with the ArcGuide™ coating was 10° (the hardest to protect). Notably, these punctures only occurred on the blades where punctures first occurred for the baseline configuration at the same angle. Blade #1 was the best performing blade in the baseline configuration and performed equally well in the ArcGuide™ configuration, therefore, no significant conclusions could be made about the performance of the ArcGuide™ coating for the angles tested. Blade #2 performed the best with the ArcGuide™ coating being the only blade configuration that passed at 10°. The results from Blade #3 are especially promising. They show that down to at least 30°, an application of the ArcGuide™ coating protected the blade, even with the disadvantage of multiple previous punctures and electrical aging from when the baseline configuration failed at all three angles tested.

4.5 Implication for Lightning Protection in the Field

Results of the initial leader attachment tests of blade tips were promising in the lab, but exactly how that translates to a reduction in lightning damage for operational wind farms is not obvious. An estimate was made based on the failure rate observed in the lab as a function of blade angle and observations of lightning attachment angles observed in the field.

In total, 154 strikes of four GE 1.5sle blade tips were conducted in the lab. For each angle and each configuration (baseline or ArcGuide™), a failure rate was calculated as the number of punctures divided by the total number of strikes (either punctures or flashovers to the receptor). This is plotted in Fig. 13. Limited testing below 10° and at 90° indicate a 100% and 0% failure rate can be assumed at these angles respectively for both configurations.

Data on the attachment angles of lightning strikes on operational wind turbines was obtained from a publication [7] that analyzed video footage of winter lightning strikes on 12 turbines over a 5-year period in Japan. The attachment angles of 172 strikes in total were quantified. The histogram in Fig.

14 shows the reported strike frequency as a function of blade angle. In this case, 90° refers to the blade extending straight up, and 0° refers to the blade extending horizontally either ascending or descending.

Fig. 13. Failure rate of baseline and ArcGuide™ configurations on GE 1.5sle blade tips as a function of blade angle from 154 initial leader attachment strikes.

Fig. 14. Histogram of attachment angles of 172 lightning strikes to 12 turbines over 5 years [7].

Of note is that 98% of strikes observed attached at a blade angle greater than 30°, and no punctures in the lab were observed with the ArcGuide™ coating at a blade angle of 30° or higher. Applying the baseline failure rate observed in the lab (linearly interpolating between angles tested) to this distribution of strikes, 6.4% of strikes would be expected to puncture through the blade skin and cause damage. Applying the ArcGuide™ failure rate to this distribution, only 1.7% of strikes (the three at 0°) would be expected to cause punctures. Thus, a 73% reduction in the frequency of punctures is predicted in the field with application of the ArcGuide™ coating for typical GE 1.5sle blades. The usual caveats about the stochasticity of lightning are relevant here and these results should be interpreted cautiously. Even with the hundreds of strikes observed in the lab and in the field for this analysis, the datasets do not appear well converged.

5. FIELD TESTS

5.1 Field Test Overview

Pilot studies with the ArcGuide™ coating are planned at two active wind farms in the United States. Both wind farms use

GE 1.5sle wind turbines and GE 37C blades. These farms have experienced high levels of lightning activity in the past few years. The ArcGuide™ coating will be applied to three to four turbines at each farm. Field service providers will perform the up-tower application of the coating. The pilot studies will occur in parallel beginning in June 2022. The turbines will be monitored for lightning damage by Arctura through at least August 2023, capturing two peak lightning seasons (i.e., June through August).

These studies serve multiple purposes. The first is to evaluate the coating's effectiveness at reducing lightning damage. Another is to evaluate its condition after continuous operation in all seasons and real-world weather conditions. Given the low number of average strikes per turbine per year and inherent stochasticity, significant quantitative results relating to lightning protection may be difficult to ascertain from the small number of initial retrofit turbines, but even anecdotal evidence will be useful. Lastly, the experience gained from real-world application will be valuable.

5.2 Field Test Monitoring

Each turbine retrofitted with the ArcGuide™ coating will be monitored for lightning strikes in three ways. First, Vaisala data from the National Lightning Detection Network will be used to determine whether a strike was likely in the vicinity of a retrofitted turbine (and all the other turbines in the farm). Second, an electromechanical lightning strike event counter will be installed on each retrofitted turbine. This device will be placed on the turbine's grounding cable in the tower base. Whenever a current exceeding the counter's threshold is detected in the cable, a mechanical display will increment. Wind farm staff will check the counter if a strike is suspected. Third, two still cameras per farm will be installed that look at the four retrofitted turbines. The cameras will be housed in a weatherproof enclosure and attached to a controller and lightning activated shutter release. When the lightning trigger senses the light pattern emitted from a stepped leader, it triggers the camera's shutter quick enough to capture the strike event. The equipment will be continuously powered by batteries and charged by either solar panels or wall power and will transfer photos via a cellular data network. Beyond confirming a probable strike, the camera will hopefully provide detail on the nature of the strike and its attachment to the wind turbine blade.

Throughout the test campaign and after potentially damaging lightning strikes, the blades will be visually assessed from the ground with a camera and telephoto lens. Additionally, photos from any drone inspections that may occur will be evaluated. Any mechanical or electrical wear or damage to the coating will be assessed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Lightning is a top cause of wind turbine blade damage, and lightning damage repairs represent a significant maintenance cost for the industry. Over three years of empirical testing and optimization in collaboration with Lightning Technologies, Arctura has developed the ArcGuide™ coating to reduce wind turbine blade lightning damage.

Compared to a baseline topcoat, the metric of average flashover time was reduced by 76% with the ArcGuide™ coating. Mechanical testing confirmed that in addition to improved electrical performance, it maintained all the utility

of an industry-standard wind turbine blade topcoat. Validation was performed on three GE 1.5sle wind turbine blade tips to IEC standards. Photos of streamers and leaders confirmed the principle of operation. Initial leader attachment tests showed the coating was effective at increasing the level of protection for this blade model. When applied to operational turbines, a 73% reduction in punctures was estimated. For other blade models, work to date shows that care must be used to determine the optimal locations for coating application so that it guides streamers and leaders only from lightning receptors, and not from other potentially susceptible conductors in the blade, where it might lead to punctures. The ArcGuide™ coating's low cost, ease of application, survivability, and negligible aerodynamic impact make it an attractive retrofit solution.

Upcoming pilot studies on operational wind farms will be used to evaluate how the ArcGuide™ coating performs over years of use in the field. Other future work is planned to evaluate interaction with carbon fiber spar caps, applicability to alternate LPS designs, and use by OEMs in new construction.

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8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science under Award Number DE-SC0018885.

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